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**FREQUENCY OF GASTROENTERITIS
AMONG PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT OF
DIFFERENT HOSPITALS**

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ABSTRACT:

Gastroenteritis, also known as infectious diarrhea and gastro, is inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract—the stomach and small intestine. Symptoms may include diarrhea, vomiting and abdominal pain. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in emergency departments of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, history of gastroenteritis and disease duration were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 100 patients included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 30.23±1.23 years. Out of 100 patients only five presented with the history of gastroenteritis including moderate to severe cases.

KEYWORDS: GASTROENTERITIS, EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

INTRODUCTION:

Gastroenteritis, also known as infectious diarrhea and gastro, is inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract—the stomach and small intestine. Symptoms may include diarrhea, vomiting and abdominal pain. Fever, lack of energy and dehydration may also occur. This typically lasts less than two weeks. It is not related to influenza, though it has erroneously been called the "stomach flu". Gastroenteritis is usually caused by viruses. However, bacteria, parasites, and fungus can also cause gastroenteritis. In children, rotavirus is the most common cause of severe disease. In adults, norovirus and Campylobacter are common causes. Eating improperly prepared food, drinking contaminated water or close contact with a person who is infected can spread the disease. Treatment is generally the same with or without a definitive diagnosis, so testing to confirm is usually not needed.

Prevention includes hand washing with soap, drinking clean water,

breastfeeding babies instead of using formula and proper disposal of human waste. The rotavirus vaccine is recommended as a prevention for children. Treatment involves getting enough fluids. For mild or moderate cases, this can typically be achieved by drinking oral rehydration solution (a combination of water, salts and sugar). In those who are breastfed, continued breastfeeding is recommended. For more severe cases, intravenous fluids may be needed. Fluids may also be given by a nasogastric tube. Zinc supplementation is recommended in children. Antibiotics are generally not needed. However, antibiotics are recommended for young children with a fever and bloody diarrhea.

In 2015, there were two billion cases of gastroenteritis, resulting in 1.3 million deaths globally. Children and those in the developing world are affected the most. In 2011, there were about 1.7 billion cases, resulting in about 700,000 deaths of children under the age of five. In the developing

world, children less than two years of age frequently get six or more infections a year. It is less common in adults, partly due to the development of immunity (1-3). The objective of this study was to see the prevalence of gastroenteritis among the patients presenting in emergency departments of different hospitals.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in emergency departments of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, history of gastroenteritis and disease duration were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 100 patients included in this study i.e., 50 males (50%) and 50 females (50%). The mean age of

the patients was 30.23 ± 1.23 years. Out of 100 patients only five presented with the history of gastroenteritis including moderate to severe cases.

DISCUSSION:

A supply of easily accessible uncontaminated water and good sanitation practices are important for reducing rates of infection and clinically significant gastroenteritis. Personal measures (such as hand washing with soap) have been found to decrease rates of gastroenteritis in both the developing and developed world by as much as 30%. Alcohol-based gels may also be effective. Food or drink that is thought to be contaminated should be avoided. Breastfeeding is important, especially in places with poor hygiene, as is improvement of hygiene generally. Breast milk reduces both the frequency of infections and their duration. Due to both its effectiveness and safety, in 2009 the World Health Organization recommended that the rotavirus vaccine be offered to

all children globally. Two commercial rotavirus vaccines exist and several more are in development. In Africa and Asia these vaccines reduced severe disease among infants and countries that have put in place national immunization programs have seen a decline in the rates and severity of disease. This vaccine may also prevent illness in non-vaccinated children by reducing the number of circulating infections. Since 2000, the implementation of a rotavirus vaccination program in the United States has substantially decreased the number of cases of diarrhea by as much as 80 percent (4-6).

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